

GridPP Dissemination and Engagement Document Index

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Abstract. The GridPP Collaboration is a community of particle physicists and computer scientists based in the United Kingdom and at CERN. This document lists the documents relating to dissemination and engagement with GridPP, including where to find them on the CERN-backed Zenodo repository (through their Digital Object Identifier) or on the Grid (through their Logical FileName in the Dirac File Catalog).

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1. Introduction

The GridPP Collaboration [1, 2] is a community of particle physicists and computer scientists based in the United Kingdom and at CERN. Drawing on expertise from nineteen UK institutions, its vision is to create, manage and oversee the evolution of the computing infrastructure needed to maintain the UK's position as a world leader in particle physics. It does this by using and actively contributing to the development of open source software, applications and middleware needed to power large-scale distributed computing for particle physics and beyond.

Since its inception in 2001, dissemination relating to the work of GridPP has been a part of the Collaboration's activities. A full history of GridPP's dissemination activities can be found in GridPP-ENG-003, the Dissemination Handbook written by Neasan O'Neill (GridPP Dissemination Officer, Jan 2008 – Jul 2013). When Tom Whyntie (Oct 2013 – Dec 2016) combined the role with that of Schools Research Champion and then STFC Public Engagement Fellow through the CERN@school research programme [3], engagement with GridPP resources became the focus of the role's activities. Further details can be found in the Dissemination Handbook Addendum (GridPP-ENG-004).

1.1. Overview

Section 2 provides an index of documents relating to Dissemination and Engagement, along with where they can be found. Public documents have been uploaded to the CERN-backed Zenodo repository[†], while collaboration documents may be found stored in the GridPP DIRAC [4, 5] DIRAC File Catalog (DFC) in the gridpp Virtual Organisation's storage space. The Logical FileName (LFN) has been provided for these; users should follow the GridPP UserGuide [6] to gain access if required.

Section 3 provides a list (Table 2) and brief summaries of engagement-related presentations given on behalf of the Collaboration since October 2013, along with links to the respective meeting pages and slides.

[†] See <http://zenodo.org>

2. Documents

Table 1 lists the Dissemination and Engagement documents, which are then briefly described in the following subsections.

Table 1: The GridPP Dissemination and Engagement documents.

DRN	Brief Title	DOI or LFN
GridPP-ENG-000	The GridPP D&E Document Index	10.5281/zenodo.223054
GridPP-ENG-001	Selected case studies	10.5281/zenodo.220995
GridPP-ENG-002	The GridPP UserGuide	10.5281/zenodo.222702
GridPP-ENG-003	The GridPP Dissemination Handbook	/gridpp/ENG/003/v1-1/diss-handbook.docx
GridPP-ENG-004	GridPP Dissemination Handbook: Addendum I	/gridpp/ENG/004/v1-0/diss-handbook-add.pdf
GridPP-ENG-005	Engagement base presentation	/gridpp/ENG/005/v1-0/pres-base.pptx
GridPP-ENG-006	Press release base document	/gridpp/ENG/006/v1-1/press-release.docx
GridPP-ENG-007	GridPP Press Release: LHC restart	/gridpp/ENG/007/v2-1/pr-lhcrestart.docx
GridPP-ENG-008	GridPP Press Release: LSST	/gridpp/ENG/008/v1-2/pr-lsst.docx
GridPP-ENG-009	Initial requirements capture proforma	/gridpp/ENG/009/v1-0/requirements.docx
GridPP-ENG-010	Collaborator's Guide to GridPP (2013)	/gridpp/ENG/010/v2-0/collab-guide.pdf
GridPP-ENG-011	GridPP poster (2011)	/gridpp/ENG/011/v1-0/poster.pdf

2.1. *The GridPP D&E Document Index*

- **Full title:** The GridPP Dissemination and Engagement document index
- **DRN:** GridPP-ENG-000
- **DOI:** [10.5281/zenodo.223054](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.223054)

This document lists all of the important documents relating to dissemination and engagement with GridPP, including where to find them on Zenodo (through their Digital Object Identifier) or on the Grid (through their Logical FileName in the Dirac File Catalog).

2.2. *Selected case studies*

- **Full title:** The GridPP New User Engagement Programme: Selected Case Studies
- **DRN:** GridPP-ENG-001
- **DOI:** [10.5281/zenodo.220995](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.220995)

A number of selected case studies from the GridPP Collaboration's New User Engagement Programme are presented, featuring new user communities from fields including medical physics, computational biology, space and astrophysics. The services used and developed by GridPP to achieve this engagement are also briefly described.

2.3. *The GridPP UserGuide*

- **Full title:** The GridPP UserGuide
- **DRN:** GridPP-ENG-002
- **DOI:** [10.5281/zenodo.222702](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.222702)

This document is an offline version of the GridPP UserGuide, written as part of GridPP's New User Engagement Programme, that aims to help new users make use of GridPP resources through the DIRAC, Ganga and CernVM suite of technologies. The online version may be found at: <http://www.gridpp.ac.uk/userguide>

2.4. *The GridPP Dissemination Handbook*

- **Full title:** GridPP Dissemination Handbook
- **DRN:** GridPP-ENG-003
- **LFN:** /gridpp/ENG/003/v1-1/diss-handbook.docx

This document is the handbook written by Neasan O'Neill (GridPP Dissemination Officer up to Summer 2013) containing everything that the GridPP Dissemination needs to know in order to perform their duties.

2.5. *GridPP Dissemination Handbook: Addendum I*

- **Full title:** GridPP Dissemination Handbook: Addendum I
- **DRN:** GridPP-ENG-004
- **LFN:** /gridpp/ENG/004/v1-0/diss-handbook-add.pdf

This document provides an addendum to the GridPP Dissemination Handbook, updating the relevant sections to reflect changes to the role since October 2013.

2.6. *Engagement base presentation*

- **Full title:** GridPP: Distributed Computing for Data-Intensive Research
- **DRN:** GridPP-ENG-005
- **LFN:** /gridpp/ENG/005/v1-0/pres-base.pptx

This Microsoft Powerpoint file provides a base presentation for use while engaging potential new users with GridPP technologies and resources. Based on a presentation by Pete Gronbech, it covers the Worldwide LHC Computing Grid, GridPP, the New User Engagement Programme and associated tools and infrastructure, and a number of selected case studies. When used, the speaker details, institute logos, and footer information should be updated accordingly. Users should also regularly check the accuracy of any figures quoted in the slides and update them accordingly.

2.7. *Press release base document*

- **Full title:** The GridPP Press Release Base Document
- **DRN:** GridPP-ENG-006
- **LFN:** /gridpp/ENG/006/v1-1/press-release.docx

This Microsoft Word document serves as a base file for creating press releases relating to GridPP activities that may attract media attention. In addition to providing the actual press release content, users should amend the contact information and verify the accuracy of the statistics quoted to reflect the current status of GridPP. Users may also wish to supply additional notes for editors for particular GridPP member institutions as appropriate; the corresponding institute's Press Office may be able to provide assistance with this if required.

2.8. *GridPP Press Release: LHC restart*

- **Full title:** Numbercrunching the LHC, round 2: GridPP ready for collider restart
- **DRN:** GridPP-ENG-007
- **LFN:** /gridpp/ENG/007/v2-1/pr-lhcrestart.docx

This press release was issued on Wednesday the 25th of March 2015 to mark the restart of the Large Hadron Collider. It is provided as an example of a press release for a Collaboration-wide story.

2.9. *GridPP Press Release: LSST*

- **Full title:** Shear brilliance: GridPP computing tackles the mystery of the dark universe
- **DRN:** GridPP-ENG-008
- **LFN:** /gridpp/ENG/008/v1-2/pr-lsst.docx

This press release was issued in November 2016, and covers the collaborative pilot project between GridPP and the Large Synoptic Survey Telescope at the University of Manchester. It is provided as an example of a press release for a site-specific story, and was released in collaboration with the University of Manchester Press Office.

2.10. *Initial requirements capture proforma*

- **Full title:** The GridPP New User Engagement Programme: Initial Requirements Capture
- **DRN:** GridPP-ENG-009
- **LFN:** /gridpp/ENG/009/v1-0/requirements.docx

This Microsoft Word document provides a proforma for performing an initial requirements capture for a new user community. It should serve only as a guideline for the process of engaging with the new user(s); experience has shown that a one-size-fits-all approach rarely succeeds when porting workflows to the Grid. Nevertheless, many potential problems can be avoided by establishing a minimum set of requirements as early as possible in the engagement process.

2.11. *Collaborator's Guide to GridPP (2013)*

- **Full title:** Collaborator's Guide to Guide
- **DRN:** GridPP-ENG-010
- **LFN:** /gridpp/ENG/010/v2-0/collab-guide.pdf

This brochure was produced in collaboration with the STFC Knowledge Transfer Network to provide an introduction to GridPP's resources for potential collaborators. It pre-dates the new GridPP website and UserGuide and perhaps needs updating accordingly. It is included for reference and posterity.

2.12. GridPP poster (2011)

- **Full title:** GridPP: UK Computing for Particle Physics (Poster, 2011)
- **DRN:** GridPP-ENG-011
- **LFN:** /gridpp/ENG/011/v1-0/poster.pdf

This poster, from 2011, provides an overview of GridPP for use at conferences and exhibitions. As it pre-dates the discovery of the Higgs boson in 2012, it should probably be updated before using it; it is included for reference and posterity.

3. Presentations

The following is a list of public presentations given as part of the Officer's work with the GridPP Collaboration and its partner organisations since October 2013. All of the featured meetings were organised via CERN's Indico system; links to the meetings and slides are provided accordingly.

Table 2: A list of the GridPP-related presentations given by the Officer. Collaboration meeting presentations are indicated with an asterisk.

Date	Title
2014-03-25 *	GridPP32: Other VOs: Review and Plans.
2014-03-26 *	GridPP32: Engaging with Smaller VOs and SMEs.
2014-05-22	EGI Community Forum 2014: the CERN@school example.
2014-05-27	Report on the EGI Community Forum 2014 for Ops.
2014-11-17	HEPSYSMAN Nov. 2014 - CERN@school DIRAC example.
2015-03-05	CernVM: Notes from GridPP.
2015-04-30 *	GridPP34: The GridUser Toolkit.
2016-01-15	HEPSYSMAN Jan. 2016 - the GridPP CernVM.
2016-04-13 *	GridPP36: new VO case study (GalDyn).
2016-06-07	CERN@school and CernVM.
2016-11-02	GridPP Infrastructure and Approaches (SKA meeting).

3.1. Collaboration Meeting 2014-03-25

- **Full title:** Other VOs: Review and Plans;
- **Date and time:** Tuesday 25 Mar 2014, 12:05 (GMT);
- **Meeting URL:** <https://indico.cern.ch/event/299622/> (slides);

This presentation provided a review of the status of the other VOs supported by GridPP, as well as their future plans.

3.2. Collaboration Meeting 2014-03-26

- **Full title:** Engaging with Smaller VOs and SMEs;
- **Date and time:** Wednesday 26 Mar 2014, 10:55 (GMT);
- **Meeting URL:** <https://indico.cern.ch/event/299622/> (slides);

This presentation presented an overview of the experiences to date with engaging smaller VOs and SMEs with GridPP technology, including a case study featuring the CERN@school LUCID simulations.

3.3. *EGI Community Forum 2014-05-22*

- **Full title:** Developing new GridPP user communities: a case study with CERN@school;
- **Date and time:** Thursday 22 May 2014, 13:05 (GMT);
- **Meeting URL:** <https://indico.egi.eu/indico/event/1994/> (slides);

This presentation to the EGI Community Forum 2014 gave an example of building a user community with the CERN@school research programme.

3.4. *Operations Meeting 2014-05-27*

- **Full title:** EGI Community Forum 2014: Engagement/Dissemination Report;
- **Date and time:** Tuesday 27 May 2014, 10:40 (GMT);
- **Meeting URL:** <http://indico.cern.ch/event/321699/> (slides);

This presentation gave a summary of the EGI Community Forum 2014 (Helsinki) from a dissemination and engagement perspective.

3.5. *HEPSYSMAN Meeting 2014-11-17*

- **Full title:** GridPP and DIRAC: an example with CERN@school;
- **Date and time:** Monday 17 Nov 2014, 13:30 (GMT);
- **Meeting URL:** <https://indico.cern.ch/event/350917/> (slides);

This presentation gave an example of a simple analysis workflow carried out using the Imperial-hosted GridPP DIRAC instance and CERN@school data and analysis software.

3.6. *CernVM Users Workshop 2015-03-05*

- **Full title:** CernVM: Notes from the GridPP new user engagement programme;
- **Date and time:** Thursday 05 Mar 2015, 15:40 (GMT);
- **Meeting URL:** <https://indico.cern.ch/event/348657/> (slides);

This presentation gave a brief overview of how the CernVM and CVMFS was being used by CERN@school as part of the New User Engagement Programme.

3.7. Collaboration Meeting 2015-04-30

- **Full title:** The GridUser Toolkit: Notes from the GridPP New User Engagement Programme;
- **Date and time:** Thursday 30 Apr 2015, 09:50 (GMT);
- **Meeting URL:** <https://indico.cern.ch/event/369153/> (slides);

The presentation gave an overview of the New User Engagement Toolkit, namely the GridPP CernVM, GridPP DIRAC, and CVMFS.

3.8. HEPSYSMAN Meeting 2016-01-15

- **Full title:** The GridPP CernVM;
- **Date and time:** Friday 15 Jan 2016, 14:30 (GMT);
- **Meeting URL:** <https://indico.cern.ch/event/465560/> (slides);

This presentation gave an overview of the GridPP CernVM as used in the New User Engagement Programme.

3.9. Collaboration Meeting 2016-04-13

- **Full title:** Supporting a new VO: A case study;
- **Date and time:** Wednesday 13 Apr 2016, 08:15 (GMT);
- **Meeting URL:** <https://indico.cern.ch/event/477023/> (slides);

This presentation described a case study of setting up a new VO through the New User Engagement Programme. The case study featured the Galactic Dynamics (GalDyn) group at the University of Central Lancashire (UCLan). Also included are the documents for performing the initial requirements capture for new user communities.

3.10. CernVM Users Workshop 2016-06-07

- **Full title:** CERN@school and CernVM;
- **Date and time:** Tuesday 07 Jun 2016, 13:00 (GMT);
- **Meeting URL:** <https://indico.cern.ch/event/469775/> (slides);

This presentation provided an update on CERN@school activities with the CernVM, focussing on how the CernVM provides a useful platform for coding in schools.

3.11. New User Community Engagement 2016-11-02

- **Full title:** GridPP Infrastructure and Approaches (SKA meeting);
- **Date and time:** Wednesday 02 Nov 2016, 11:10 (GMT);
- **Meeting URL:** <https://indico.cern.ch/event/570594/> (slides);

This presentation, given at the SKA/GridPP meeting at the University of Manchester, provided an overview of GridPP and the services and infrastructure it could potentially offer members of the Square Kilometre Array telescope collaboration.

References

- [1] The GridPP Collaboration. GridPP: Development of the UK Computing Grid for Particle Physics. *J. Phys. G*, 32:N1–N20, 2006.
- [2] D. Britton et al. GridPP: the UK grid for particle physics. *Phil. Trans. R. Soc. A*, 367:2447–2457, 2009.
- [3] T. Whyntie et al. CERN@school: bringing CERN into the classroom. *Nucl. Part. Phys. Proc.*, 273–275:1265–1270, 2016.
- [4] D. Bauer et al. The GridPP DIRAC project: Implementation of a multi-VO DIRAC service. *J. Phys.: Conf. Ser.*, 664:062009, 2015.
- [5] D. Bauer et al. The GridPP DIRAC project - DIRAC for non-LHC communities. *J. Phys.: Conf. Ser.*, 664:062036, 2015.
- [6] T. Whyntie. The GridPP UserGuide. *Zenodo*, doi:10.5281/zenodo.222702, 2016.

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Version History

Table 3: Version history.

Version	Description	DOI	Author
1.0	Initial version.	10.5281/zenodo.223054	TW